

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 1, March - 2024 | Peer-Reviewed
Journal ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12607575

THE CHALLENGES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS FROM EAD TRAINING

AUTHOR

Catarina Gama (catymestrado@yahoo.com): Master's Student of the Universidad UNIDA Program, Professor of the Physical Education course at Unopar. High School Physical Education Teacher.

ABSTRACT

This study addresses teacher training and intervention in Physical Education, focusing on the challenges of distance learning. Initially, the historical evolution of Physical Education training in Brazil is discussed, from its military origins to its incorporation into the school curriculum and its transformations. The National Education Guidelines and Bases Law (LDB) of 1996 introduced distance learning as a teaching modality at all levels, including undergraduate courses in Physical Education. The objectives are to reflect on the role of distance learning teachers in teacher training, analyze the acceptance of the distance learning training proposal by educational institutions and highlight the lack of practical bodily experience in their training. The theoretical foundation focuses on teacher training, interdisciplinarity, the importance of pedagogical practice articulated with theory and the need to develop professional skills. The methodology consists of a bibliographic review. Critical analysis of the results seeks to identify trends, gaps in the literature and divergent perspectives. The results highlight the challenges faced by Physical Education teachers trained in distance learning. The conclusion highlights the importance of the continuous search for knowledge, reflection on overcoming challenges in acting, whether in face-to-face or distance learning.

INTRODUCTION

The educational context is increasingly demanding constant discussions about teacher training and intervention, which requires improvement and updates to the teaching-learning process. With the advancement of technological resources, distance learning (EaD) has become a real possibility and is increasingly sought after in Brazil, as it is a real possibility that guarantees access to higher education for those who work and/or do not have access to a lot of time, for various reasons, to dedicate to face-to-face teaching. However, there are many challenges arising from distance learning within the scope of the initial training of Physical Education teachers, especially during their professional career.

Training physical education teachers is a complex and challenging process, which must encompass the different aspects of the profession, from theoretical and methodological foundations to pedagogical practice, knowing that this is an essential process for the quality of school physical education.

Physical education, as well as its professional training, over the years has undergone several changes following human, cultural, social and technological evolution. However, to understand how this training is based today, we need to go back in time, when physical education began here in Brazil as a military practice, where training took place through short courses. After 1822, in the Imperial period, physical education began to be incorporated into the school curriculum, but still with a military focus. Physical education schools were created by military institutions, and training was aimed at preparing teachers for military education. In 1889, during the republican period, Physical Education began to be seen as an activity with educational purposes, aimed at the physical and moral development of citizens. Physical Education schools began to be created by civil institutions, and training began to include subjects such as psychology, pedagogy and sociology. After 1930, Physical Education underwent a series of transformations, with the influence of new pedagogical and sporting currents. The training of Physical

Education teachers became broader and more diverse, including subjects such as the history of Physical Education, teaching methodology and assessment.

LDB in 1996 introduced distance learning as the teaching modality at all levels. This type of teaching has been gaining new forms and merits, contributing ever since to the cultural, social and civic development of its followers. The Physical Education undergraduate course began to be offered in this format in Brazil in 2011, with the publication of Resolution CNE/CES n° 5, of November 19, 2011. This resolution established the curricular guidelines for Physical Education courses. degree in Physical Education, both in-person and distance learning .

As a starting point, this research will specifically address the challenges encountered in the practical work of Physical Education teachers trained through distance learning . A pertinent issue that we can list in this relationship deals with the way in which ICTs are incorporated into education to be the central element (or facilitator, or even “mediator”) in the training of distance teachers, bringing from limiting aspects to the possibilities that these artifacts Technological technologies can provide qualified teacher training to work in basic education .

In view of this, a concern arose as to whether the physical education teacher who leaves initial training in the EAD format demonstrates sufficient preparation to be in charge of a classroom, even knowing that training through distance learning brings the advantage to enhance the interaction of participants through the internet, where according to Gouveia (2007) we live in a society that is interaction, training and knowledge. And all these aspects are achieved in a distance learning training course.

This study has the general objective of identifying the challenges faced by physical education teachers, trained through distance learning, in their teaching activities. Three specific objectives were also established:

- Reflect on the role of the distance learning

teacher, in contributing to the training of physical education teachers.

- Analyze the acceptance of the distance learning training proposal by regular education institutions.
- Highlight the lack of practical bodily experience in distance learning training for Physical Education teachers.

METHODOLOGY

In this study, a comprehensive literature review was carried out to examine the existing literature on the challenges of physical education teachers coming from distance learning. The literature review methodology followed a systematic approach, starting with a clear definition of the theme and objectives of the review. Next, the main relevant bibliographic databases were identified and appropriate search strategies were developed, using keywords and specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. After the search, the sources were carefully selected based on their relevance to the study, being subjected to a critical and analytical analysis to identify trends, gaps in the literature and divergent perspectives. The results were synthesized in a clear and coherent way, following an appropriate structure for the article, and were carefully reviewed before submission to ensure the accuracy and quality of the literature review carried out.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Teaching training has its own nature, which comes from the interrelationship between teaching, research and extension, and is fully linked to knowing and doing, theory and practice, research and educational intervention in different tasks. and dimensions of man, mediated by human corporeality, in its personal and social collective sense, now called Physical Education. Training teachers means outlining a type of public intellectual who must deal with human corporeality in its concrete and sensitive, technical and aesthetic aspects, with the aim of promoting transformations in the behavior and political and moral values of new generations.

Distance learning has been growing rapidly

in Brazil, with the most diverse course offerings, mainly within undergraduate degrees, as a way of enabling access to higher education for those people who do not have enough time available to dedicate themselves to higher education training. in person, and also to facilitate access to college for those who live in regions far from cities that have a higher education institution. Since 2010, the Degree in Physical Education course in this teaching modality has fueled a clash between critics of the distance learning modality for the Physical Education professional course and defenders of this teaching modality. The Federal Council of Physical Education – CONFEF1, in 2018, took a stand against the offerings of undergraduate courses in Physical Education along the lines of EaD2, mainly the bachelor's degree course, but also opposing the degree course, alleging an inability to train professionals with compatible skills. for professional development based on the training obtained through the distance learning modality in its entirety. Some research authors in the area, such as: Freitas (2007), Alonso (2010), among others, believe that this training model can be considered very fragile, due to several factors, including the lack of infrastructure available to undergraduates. Through the authors' conception, we can see the importance of identifying, from the perception of Physical Education professionals, the impacts and challenges of training in the distance learning modality in relation to the training skills and competencies in the quality of learning of undergraduates in the training area.

Teacher training resulting from distance learning must provide practical experience, since pedagogical practice must be understood as an articulated expression of theory with socio-educational reality, aiming to streamline conceptual aspects and pedagogical intervention in the real world. This dimension must be present in the curricular components, articulated with the contents of body culture and with the pedagogical practice of Physical Education at school (Early Childhood Education, and Elementary and Secondary Education).

Physical education is a course that has the particularity of experimenting with bodily practices, which is of fundamental importance

that its experience is carried out by associating it with theory, being a field that covers various areas of knowledge such as “pedagogy, physiology, sociology, biomechanics, kinesiology” (NUNES and FRAGA, 2005). In the role of the teacher, Tardif (2012) states that the knowledge of teachers is not just theoretical knowledge, the teacher in their daily lives is a builder of knowledge, producing knowledge, instructing and educating students for life.

In order for educators to gradually develop their professional competence, it is essential that they approach their practice by generating pedagogical knowledge while planning, investigating, evaluating and collaborating with their colleagues, designing interventions that promote student progress. More than assimilating theoretical knowledge about education, it is crucial that the educator adopts a stance that permeates his educational practice and leads him to an attitude of reflection in the face of educational challenges, leading him to deal meticulously and attentively and to critically analyze their own view of the nature of the learning process, as the objective is for the student to learn and for the educator to guide this learning process.

The educator must primarily have knowledge about what he will teach, and his training must result from an interdisciplinary approach, as this requires him to have the ability to master knowledge that goes beyond his specialization in a single discipline. Interdisciplinarity can be considered as a new way of understanding knowledge and the teaching process, that is, a new guiding principle for the reorganization of various areas of study and the reformulation of pedagogical structures. When acting, educators need to seek innovations, redefine their criteria, modify their perspectives and, above all, cultivate critical thinking that leads them to question their knowledge considered officially valid, critically recreating the content they transmit.

RESULTS

Much has been questioned about the most diverse challenges encountered in the role of professionals, trained in distance learning, in the

teaching/learning process presented in schools. And in order for us to achieve an improvement in the quality of basic teacher training, it is necessary for this professional to undergo critical reflective training, which constitutes a process of relating knowledge and knowledge with the teacher's personal identity. This process, according to Garcia (1999, pg.19) can be understood as: “... a process of development and structuring of the person that takes place with the double effect of internal maturation and possibilities of learning, of experience of the subjects.”

Therefore, the teacher must act as a trainer and trainee. It is observed that the training of teaching professional development, when based on technique, does not produce reflective, autonomous professionals who take responsibility for their professional development, thus, the challenges encountered by physical education teachers are found, in insecurity in their performance, the lack of practical experience in the teacher training process directly reflects on their mastery and class planning, thus generating a reflection on the experience of the mandatory curricular internship, which is of utmost importance in professional training courses. This is the moment that teachers in training will be able to reflect on their professional future, knowing the reality they will face when they graduate.

CONCLUSION

The teaching-learning process, whether distance learning or face-to-face, involves individuals, each with their own peculiarities and particular needs. Each person brings with them their own life story, their experiences and motivations in addition to their cultural background, and often, students who cannot attend a face-to-face course find distance learning courses an alternative to continue their lives within their studies. From the participants in the research conducted to prepare the article “The challenges of physical education teachers from distance learning training Training of Physical Education teachers in the EaD modality: integration into school culture through supervised internship”, none had previous experience in teaching, or any other practice of less similarity. It

was clear that there would be many doubts about how to proceed within the classroom as a teacher, how to deal with the unpredictable situations of teaching practice, and these doubts would also arise if the students were in a face-to-face course. Therefore, it would not be correct to attribute the difficulties encountered by the teachers, already at the time, just to the fact that the students were present. in a distance course without practical experience in the classroom. Considering that studying a distance degree, in any area, does not imply studying less or doing things negligently, a distance learning student must have the following in their curriculum. same content, if not more, than a face-to-face student, in addition to requiring a greater discipline of always having to look for sources of knowledge and opportunities to develop practice, since you will also have introductory subjects that prepare you for this modality.

What is fundamental is to recognize our need to seek knowledge and reflect on it, in addition to always being aware of the need for interaction in the teaching-learning processes. Gouveia suggests that this interaction can be expanded via the internet. The same author highlights that we live in a society that is not just marked by interaction.

Thinking about the Physical Education teacher; which is no different from a teacher from another area, as this teacher must also be a research and reflective teacher. A distance teacher training course is capable of training a Physical Education teacher as necessary; provided that the supervised curricular internship is a criterion in the same way as this occurs in a face-to-face teacher training course; because that is where the teacher begins to be born; living the practice. The teacher is trained throughout his life, from the time he passes through the school to his direct and continuous contact with the student. It is in practice that the teacher builds his knowledge, it is in work that the professional grows by doing his reflections and research based on his needs, creating autonomy to make the necessary decisions.

It is important to highlight that no one is born a teacher, but one learns to be a teacher,

and the challenges encountered will be daily, which is why it is necessary for the teacher to live in constant reflection on his/her practical performance, seeking solutions to the most diverse challenges encountered in his/her work. day to day. The Physical Education teacher has fundamental importance in the process of training students, and he must seek ways for the teaching-learning process, even if obstacles arise along the way that, with his training base and reflective thinking, can be overcome.

REFERENCES

BRAZIL. Federal Law No. 9,394 of December 20, 1996. Provides for the Guidelines and Bases of National Education. Brasilia DF. 2000.

LAZZAROTTI FILHO, ARI et al. Teacher training in distance learning: Physical Education and its specificity. 2009.

MARCELO GARCIA, Carlos. Teacher training. For Educational Change. Porto: Porto publisher. 1999. Professional Development: Past and Future. *Sísifo – Revista das Ciências de Educação* n° 8 page. 22 Jan /Apr. 2009. Available at: <http://cev.org.br/biblioteca/diretrizes-curriculares-formacao-profissional-educacao-fisica-um-estudo-introdutorio/> accessed on 06/15/2013.

NUNES, Rute Viegas. FRAGA, Alex Branco. Astral Alignment: The Teaching Internship in the Training of Graduates in Physical Education at ESEF/ UFRGS. Thinking about Practice: magazine of the Faculty of Physical Education/ Federal University of Goiás. Vol. 9, n.2, Jul./Dec. 2006-. Goiânia: Ed. UFG.

ROSA, Wilton Célio. Training of physical education teachers: in-person and distance learning. 2014.

TARDIF, Maurice. Teaching Knowledge and Professional Training, 13th Ed. Petrópolis RJ: Vozes, 2012.